

Recent Regulatory Submissions Using RWD in Oncology

By Philip He, PhD† and Laura Fernandes, PhD‡

Table 1 lists the recent regulatory submissions using RWD to FDA in oncology. The ODAC meeting on October 4, 2023 is particularly interesting about eflornithine in high-risk neuroblastoma who have completed multiagent, multimodality therapy, where external control arm was used to demonstrate the significant effectiveness. In this case, the natural history of the disease has been established by prior clinical trials and external control data source is clinical trial data, verified by FDA inspections. The ODAC voting was 14:6 in favor of eflornithine improving event-free survival and FDA approved the indication in December 2023. Wang et al (2023) summarized the EMA oncology approvals using external controls from 2016 to 2021 (Table 2). According to this publication, from 2019 to 2021, among 7 oncology drugs with conditional approval (tafasitamab, idecabtagene vicleucel, trastuzumab deruxtecan, belantamab mafodotin, entrectinib, brexucabtagene autoleucel, cemiplimab), EMA accepted the RWD only in some cases. All RWD accepted cases are for understanding of historical benchmark or natural history of disease, except for cemiplimab where RWD was used for comparative efficacy analysis.

Table 1. Recent Regulatory Submissions Using RWD in Oncology (FDA)

Drug	Therapeutic Area	Year	RWD Source	RWD Use
Blinatumomab ¹	Ph+ R/R B-cell precursor (BCP) ALL	2014	CRF from trials sites	ECA for SA trial
Avelumab ²	Metastatic Merkel cell carcinoma (MCC)	2017	EHR and registry data	ECA for SA trial
Blinatumomab ³	(MRD+) ALL R/R BCP	2018	CRF from trials sites	ECA for SA trial
Pembrolizumab and lenvatinib ⁴	Endometrial carcinoma	2019	Historical controls	Isolation of treatment effect
Selinexor ⁵	Relapsed refractory multiple myeloma (RRMM)	2019	EHR	ECA for SA trial
Erdafitinib ⁶	FGFR2/3+ mUC	2019	EHR data from US community-based cancer clinics	ECA for SA trial
Palbociclib ⁷	Breast cancer males	2019	EHR	ECA for SA trial
Idecabtagene Vicleucel ⁸	Multiple Myeloma	2020	Pooled EHR data	ECA for SA trial
Selumetinib ⁹	Neurofibromatosis type 1 with inoperable plexiform neurofibromas (pediatric)	2020	Historical controls	Establish natural history
Omburtamab ¹⁰	Neuroblastoma	2022	Central German Childhood Cancer Registry	ECA for SA trial
Eflornithine ¹¹	High-risk neuroblastoma	2023	Historical clinical trial data	ECA for SA trial

Note: This list is not exhaustive. SA = single arm

Table 2. Summary of Cancer Drug Approvals Using External Controls (EMA)

Drug	Therapeutic Area	Year	RWD Source	RWD Use	Conditional Approval	EMA Decision on External Control
Tafasitamab	Lymphoma	2021	RWD	Comparative efficacy analysis	Yes	Rejected
Idecabtagene vicleucel	Multiple Myeloma	2021	RWD	Comparative efficacy analysis	Yes	Rejected
Trastuzumab deruxtecan	Breast Neoplasms	2021	RWD, Published observational studies	Comparative efficacy analysis, Understanding the natural history of disease	Yes	Rejected comparative efficacy, accepted natural history of disease
Belantamab mafodotin	Multiple Myeloma	2020	Published observational studies	Historical benchmark	Yes	Accepted
Entrectinib	Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer	2020	RWD	Comparative efficacy analysis	Yes	Rejected
Brexucabtagene autoleucel	Lymphoma	2020	Published observational studies	Historical benchmark	Yes	Accepted
Brexucabtagene autoleucel	Lymphoma	2020	Published observational studies	Historical benchmark	Yes	Rejected
Cemiplimab	Squamous Cell Carcinoma	2019	RWD	Comparative efficacy analysis	Yes	Accepted
Apealea (paclitaxel)	Ovarian Neoplasms	2018	Historical clinical trials	Defining margin of non-inferiority	No	Accepted
Abemaciclib	Breast Neoplasms	2018	Unspecified	Historical benchmark, Comparative efficacy analysis	No	Accepted historical benchmark, rejected comparative efficacy
Axicabtagene ciloleucel	Lymphoma	2018	RWD and historical clinicamized trials	Comparative efficacy analysis	No	Accepted
Avelumab	Neuroendocrine Tumors	2017	RWD	Understanding the natural history of disease	No	Accepted
Dimutuximab beta	Neuroblastoma	2017	RWD, Historical clinical trials	Comparative efficacy analysis	No	Accepted
Midostaurin	Leukemia, Mastocytosis	2017	Historical clinical trials	Comparative efficacy analysis	No	Rejected
Atezolizumab	Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer	2017	Historical clinical trials	Historical benchmark	No	Rejected
	Urologic Neoplasms	2017	RWD	Historical benchmark	No	Rejected
Chlormethine	Mycosis Fungoides	2017	Unspecified	Defining margin of non-inferiority	No	Accepted
Rituximab	Lymphoma, Leukemia	2017	Historical clinical trials	Comparative efficacy analysis, Defining margin of non-inferiority	No	Accepted
Daratumumab	Multiple Myeloma	2016	Published observational studies	Historical benchmark	No	Accepted

Source: Wang et al 2023.

†Daiichi Sankyo Inc. ‡COTA, Inc.

References:

[1]FDA Review Blinatumomab 2014. Accessed March 30, 2024, https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2014/125557Orig1s000MedRedt.pdf.
 [2]FDA CDER Multi-disciplinary Review Avelumab 2017. Accessed March 30, 2024 https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2017/761049Orig1s000MultidisciplineR.pdf.
 [3]FDA Review Blinatumomab 2018. Accessed March 30, 2024 https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2018/125557Orig1s013.pdf.
 [4]Mishra-Kalyani et al. External control arms in oncology: current use and future directions. Ann Oncol. 2022 Apr;33(4):376-383. doi: 10.1016/j.annonc.2021.12.015.
 [5]FDA Review Selinexor 2019. Accessed March 30, 2024 https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2019/212306Orig1s000MultidisciplineR.pdf.
 [6]FDA Review Erdafitinib 2019. Accessed March 30, 2024, https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2019/212018Orig1s000OtherR.pdf.
 [7]FDA Review Palbociclib 2019. Accessed March 30, 2024, https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2019/207103Orig1s008.pdf.
 [8]Jagannath et al. KarMMA-RW: comparison of idecabtagene vicleucel with real-world outcomes in relapsed and refractory multiple myeloma. Blood Cancer J. 2021
 [9]ODAC FDA Briefing Document Omburtamab 2022. Accessed March 30, 2024, <https://www.fda.gov/media/162614/download>
 [10]ODAC FDA Briefing Document Eflornithine 2023. Accessed March 30, 2024, <https://www.fda.gov/media/172661/download>
 [11]Wang X, Dormont F, Lorenzato C, Latouche A, Hernandez R, Rouzier R. Current perspectives for external control arms in oncology clinical trials: Analysis of EMA approvals 2016-2021. J Cancer Policy. 2023 Mar;35:100403. doi: 10.1016/j.jcpo.2023.100403. Epub 2023 Jan 14. PMID: 36646208.

References for the Cover Page:

[1]FDA Real-World Evidence <https://www.fda.gov/science-research/science-and-research-special-topics/real-world-evidenc>. Accessed 27 March 2024
 [2]Ventz et al. The design and evaluation of hybrid controlled trials that leverage external data and randomization. Nat Commun 13, 5783 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33192-1>
 [3]Zhu et al. Hybrid clinical trials to generate real-world evidence: design considerations from a sponsor's perspective. Contemp Clin Trials. 2020 Jul;94:105856. doi: 10.1016/j.cct.2019.105856.
 [4]Evans et al. Real-World Data for Planning Eligibility Criteria and Enhancing Recruitment: Recommendations from the Clinical Trials Transformation Initiative. Ther Innov Regul Sci. 2021 May;55(3):545-552. doi: 10.1007/s43441-020-00248-7.
 [5]Kc et al. What, Where, and How to Collect Real-World Data and Generate Real-World Evidence to Support Drug Reimbursement Decision-Making in Asia: A reflection Into the Past and A Way Forward. Int J Health Policy Manag. 2023;12:6858. doi: 10.34172/ijhpm.2023.6858.
 [6]Graili et al. Integration of real-world evidence from different data sources in health technology assessment. J Pharm Pharm Sci. 2023 Jul 17;26:11460. doi: 10.3389/jpps.2023.11460.
 [7]Emmott et al. Duke-Margolis Whitepaper: Improving Patient Subgroup Representation with Real-World Data Real World Efficacy and Patient Subgroups. September 28, 2023. Accessed March 27, 2024. <https://healthpolicy.duke.edu/publications/improving-patient-subgroup-representation-real-world-data>
 [8]FDA's Sentinel Initiative. 2019 <https://www.fda.gov/safety/fdas-sentinel-initiative>. Accessed 27 March 2024.
 [9]Voss et al. European Health Data & Evidence Network—learnings from building out a standardized international health data network. Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association, 2024, 209-219, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocad214>